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Multiple Choice Questions in Higher Secondary Examination in Bangladesh: A Comparative Evaluation by Year and Stream

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Abstract

Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) represent a substantial portion of the High Secondary Certificate (HSC) score distribution in Bangladesh, directly influencing admissions to tertiary education. Despite their crucial role, a 10% reduction in MCQs was enacted in 2018 without evaluating the ongoing psychometric validity or coverage trade-offs. Using Classical Test Theory (CTT) and Item Response Theory (IRT) approaches, this study evaluated MCQ data from 1,000 randomly selected students across two changeover years (2016 vs. 2018) and three educational streams (science, humanities, and business studies). Results showed consistently good reliability in 2016 but poor metrics in 2018. Mean item difficulty remained moderate, but item discriminability suffered markedly in 2018, particularly alongside a general poor fit in the person-item maps. The empirical evidence confirms that MCQ testing is a moderately valid method, meaning the sudden item reduction was unjustified. The authors conclude that test developers require rigorous, regular psychometric and educational measurement training

Multiple Choice Questions in Higher Secondary Examination in Bangladesh: A Comparative Evaluation by Year and Stream

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Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) are globally used to assess students' knowledge and progress from a wide content coverage yet in a short time and in a form of an objective assessment. The score distribution of Secondary and Higher Secondary (SSC and HSC) Examinations in Bangladesh consist of 25% to 40% marks to MCQs. Admission tests in tertiary education (e.g., public universities and medical colleges) sets minimum Grade Point Averages (GPAs) of SSC and HSC examinations as application criteria. Furthermore, varying weights on GPAs are given toward making merit position for enrolment. It appears that the MCQ test plays a crucial role in high stake public examination and higher education admission test. However, the MCQs in HSC Examination have never been evaluated after their introduction. Additionally, the number of MCQs has been suddenly reduced by 10% in 2018 without examining the trade-off between content coverage and content quality in using MCQs. The present study, therefore, addressed the issue by assessing and comparing reliability, validity, item difficulty, item discrimination and person-item map between two changeover years (2016 and 2018) and three educational streams (science, humanities, and business) adopting Classical Test Theory (CTT) and Item Response Theory (IRT) approaches. The reliability coefficient was consistently good in 2016 but poor in 2018 for all three streams. The concurrent validity coefficient (correlation between MCQ and CQ) was less than optimal (0.55 as recommended by Smith & Smith, 2005) with fairly similar across years and streams. The mean difficulty was mostly moderate irrespective of the year and stream, mean discriminability was mostly fair to good for 2016 but poor to fair for 2018 with highest for science, followed by humanities and then business studies. The person-item map mapping ability of persons (students) in relation to difficulty of items (questions) was found to exhibit a poor fit in general. Overall findings prove MCQ testing a moderately valid method and falsify the whimsical MCQ reduction as a justified step. It is concluded that greater importance should be placed on imparting rigorous training to test makers on educational measurement and psychometrics on a regular basis. The findings have implications for teachers, educators, and policy makers.

Keywords: Multiple Choice Questions, Classical Test Theory, Item Response Theory, Item Difficulty, Item Discrimination, Person-Item Map

Multiple Choice Questions are widely used on high stake examination around the world across school, colleges and universities and they often share a substantial portion of students' achievement scores (Mavis, Cole, & Hoppe, 2001; McDougall, 1997). Generally, a Multiple Choice Questions (MCQ) includes a question stem and a set of two or more options that consist of possible answers to the question.

The test taker need to select the best option from the options provided. The correct or best answer often termed as key and the remaining alternatives as distractors (Cizek, & O'Day, 1994). Distractors are provided to distinguish from students who do not acquired sufficient knowledge or have partial knowledge to identify the correct answer.

The MCQ format offers many advantages.

It allows teachers to efficiently assess large numbers of students with minimal human intervention, less time, easy and quick analysis employing optically scanning machine (DiBattista & Kurzawa, 2011; Mc Coubrie, 2004). Further, well-constructed MCQ test can yield reliable test scores and allow to cover broader topics of a course (Downing, 2002; Bacon, 2003). In spite these advantages, MCQ testing approach also carries a number of critical reviews. Several studies (Walsh & Seldomridge, 2006; Masters et al., 2001) found that MCQs may predominately measure factual information and often ill-suited for testing higher-order cognitive skills. However, evident (Buckles & Siegfried, 2006; Palmer & Devitt, 2007) indicated that well-written MCQ items can measure students' higher-level cognitive processes.

Furthermore, MCQs with appropriate psychometric property estimate accurate differences between high-and-low achieving students (Downing, 2002; Schuwirth, & van der Vleuten, 2003). Good item construction is critical since test grades affect students' educational outcomes and subsequent career paths (Tarrant, Knierim, Hayes, & Ware, 2006). Contrarily, well-constructed MCQ items are time consuming and difficult to write, and it is estimated that a good MCQ may require about one hour to construct (Farley, 1989). Teachers often spend a great deal of time constructing the stem and much less time on developing probable options. High quality MCQ requires the plausible options to be well written (Haladyna, & Downing, 1989). Poorly constructed options or distractors frequently contain clues/cues that allow students to guess the correct answer without the prerequisite knowledge and as a result, the item poorly discriminates between high-and-low achieving students (Downing, 2002; Biggs, 1999). Di Battista & Kurzawa (2011) reported that if "as the number of functional distractors in MC items increased, discriminatory power increased and items became more difficult" (p.19).

It appears that several factors need to be considered evaluating the quality of MCQs and need to examine how each of the items conform to standard item-writing guidelines (Haladyna,

Downing, & Rodriguez, 2002). Another way to evaluate the quality of MCQ items involves analysing the responses that examinees make. MCQ testing has been a part of public examinations in Bangladesh. The first MCQ tests were included at the Secondary School Certificate Examinations. About 25% to 40% marks are currently allocated for MCQs on public examinations namely on HSC and SSC. These tests are developed by teachers teaching the courses. However, a few teachers have proper education and adequate training in developing high-quality MCQs. Teachers either develop MCQs themselves or rely on MCQ test-banks as a source of questions, both of which may result in question.

Rationale of the Study

Higher Secondary Certificate Examination is one of the most important public examinations in Bangladesh. It is a high-stakes test having important consequences for the test taker in terms of getting selection and placement of higher education and determining future career path development. The score of higher secondary public examination carries a substantial share from MCQ scores of the examination. There is a common debate that MCQ assessment method may have contributor in falling the quality of education of higher secondary education (Chowdhury et al., 2016). This belief is further reinforced by the assumption that there are substantial deficiencies on the part of the teachers preparing MCQs. The main purpose of this study therefore was to examine the quality of the test as a whole and individual MCQ. Specifically, we analysed MCQs on HSC Examination in 2018 and 2016 focusing on two key parameters of MCQ - difficulty level and discrimination index.

Objectives of the study:

The general objective of the present study was to evaluate MCQs of the selected subjects (Bangla, ICT, Physics, Civics, and Management) in HSC examinations across years (2016 versus 2018) and streams (science, humanities, and business studies). The specific objectives were as follows:

- To evaluate and compare coefficient alpha by year and Stream.
- To evaluate and compare difficulty level by year and Stream.
- To evaluate and compare discriminatory power by year and stream.
- To evaluate and compare person-item map by year and stream.

Method

Data Collection

The present study considered secondary data for analysis. Complete responses of randomly selected 1000 students each in Bangla (Compulsory), ICT (Compulsory), Physics (Science), Civics (Humanities), and Management (Business) for 2016 and 2018 HSC Examinations were collected from Dhaka Education Board. The following inclusion criteria were considered for the secondary data collected:

- Examinees who answered all the MCQs in selected subjects
- Examinees representing male and female
- Examinees representing urban, semiurban, and rural institutions

Data Analysis

Apart from computing mean, standard deviation etc., we computed the following:

Test Reliability: Coefficient alpha as internal consistency reliability was computed.

Test Validity: Coefficient of correlation between total MCQ and CQ was computed to represent concurrent validity of the test.

Item Difficulty: The difficulty (or facility) of an item was determined by computing PC. The PC denotes the percentage or proportion of students answering the correct option of an item or question. The recommended range of P is 0.31 to 0.70 (Bichi, 2015). However, the following classification scheme was adopted for the present study:

$$P_c = \frac{\text{No of students answering the item correctly}}{\text{Total no of students}} \dots(1)$$

Table 1. Classification of item difficulty using CTT approach

Item Difficulty Index	Interpretation
Less than .30	Difficult
.31 to Less than .70	Moderately Difficult
.> 0.70	Easy

Item Discriminability: Item discrimination can be determined by computing Upper-Lower Index (ULIC), point-biserial correlation (PBC) between item and total, and corrected point biserial correlation (CPBC). We adopted CPBC in the present study. The difference between PBC and CPBC is that the correlation in latter case is calculated between the item and the total excluding the item in question. This correction is made because total scores that have the item in question embedded within them will have a spuriously higher relationship (i.e., correlation). The following cut-offs were used in the present study where CPBC > .35 (excellent), .25 ≤ CPBC < .35 (good), .15 ≤ CPBC < .25 (fair), 0.0 ≤ CPBC < .15 (poor), and CPBC < 0.0 (Miskeyed or Other Flaws).

$$cPB_c = \frac{M_c - M}{S} \sqrt{\frac{P_c}{1 - P_c}} \dots(2)$$

Where M_c is the mean score on the criterion (total test score) of the examinees who answered the item correctly; M and S are the mean and standard deviation on the criterion of all the examinees; and P_c is the proportion of the examinees who answered the item correctly.

Person-Item Map was provided by Rasch Model using ConQuest software.

Results

The present study evaluated MCQs of Bangla, ICT, Physics, Civics, and Management of HSC examinations in 2016 and 2018. Each question comprised of four options where one of them was the correct answer or key and remaining three were distractors. The number of questions given and analysed in each subject is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Number of questions analysed and given in HSC examinations

Code	Subject	2016		2018	
		Analysed	Given	Analysed	Given
101	Bangla	29	40	25	30
275	ICT	34	35	25	25
174	Physics	32	35	25	25
269	Civics	40	40	30	30
277	Management	38	40	30	30

We computed coefficient alpha as an index of internal consistency reliability and correlation between MCQ and CQ as concurrent validity. The coefficients are presented in Table 3. The coefficient alpha in five subjects ranged from 0.69 to 0.86 in 2016 and from 0.52 to 0.74 in 2018. It is evident that reliability coefficients of MCQs in 2016 were higher in all subjects than those in 2018. Specifically, coefficients were questionable to good in 2016 and poor to acceptable in 2018 according to the tiered cut-off approach suggested by George and Mallery (2003). They suggested the following: " $\geq .9$ – Excellent, $\geq .8$ – Good, $\geq .7$ – Acceptable, $\geq .6$ – Questionable, $\geq .5$ – Poor, and $\leq .5$ – Unacceptable" (p. 231). While a lower cut-off (i.e., 0.70) is appropriate for early scale development, a more strict cutoffs can be applied for basic (0.80 or higher) and applied research

(0.90 or higher) (Nunnally, 1978; Lance et al., 2006). Other study (Hair et al., 2010) remarks that a value of 0.70 could be acceptable value and values as low as 0.60 may be acceptable for exploratory research.

While computing difficulty and discrimination indices, we considered only those questions having one correct option and excluded those having none or more than one correct option. The distributions of difficulty and discrimination indices are presented in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4 shows that about 50% to 80% of the items were in moderate. Among 3 streams namely science, humanities, and business, percentage of easy questions was highest for Management (36.67% to 57.89%), followed by for Civics (35% to 40%), and lowest for Physics (0.00% to 9.38%). Comparing between years, 2018 contained higher percentage of difficult questions than 2016.

Table 5 shows that about 50% to 90% of the items were fair to excellent in DI across subjects and years. Further inspection revealed that generally a greater number of MCQs was flaw to poor in DI in 2018 and it was more prominent in Management (46.66%), Bangla (36%), ICT (36%) and Physics (28%).

Test difficulty and discrimination indices as calculated by averaging indices of constituent items of each subject reflects that Management

Table 3. Coefficients of reliability (alpha) and validity (correlation between MCQ and CQ)

Subject	Year	Coefficient Alpha	Remark	r (N = 1000)
Bangla	2016	0.81 (29)	Good	0.55
	2018	0.59 (25)	Poor	0.41
ICT	2016	0.69 (34)	Questionable	0.46
	2018	0.60 (25)	Questionable	0.49
Physics	2016	0.86 (32)	Good	0.48
	2018	0.69 (25)	Questionable	0.62
Civics	2016	0.78 (40)	Acceptable	0.42
	2018	0.74 (30)	Acceptable	0.45
Management	2016	0.73 (38)	Acceptable	0.37
	2018	0.52 (30)	Poor	0.34

Note. Values in parenthesis in column coefficient alpha indicates no of items or questions analyzed

Table 4. Range, Mean, Frequency, and Percentage of p values falling in each category of difficulty for each subject by year

Subject	Year	Range	Mean	P ≤ .30 = Difficult		.31 ≤ .70 = Moderately Difficult		P > .70 = Easy		Total
				f	%	f	%	f	%	
				Bangla	2016	.18 – .80	.55	02	6.90	
	2018	.19 – .81	.49	06	24.00	15	60.00	04	16.00	25
ICT	2016	.13 – .98	.50	08	23.53	18	52.94	08	23.53	34
	2018	.19 – .78	.41	08	32.00	16	64.00	01	4.00	25
Physics	2016	.12 – .81	.50	03	9.38	26	81.25	03	9.38	32
	2018	.10 – .70	.38	08	32.00	17	68.00	00	0.00	25
Civics	2016	.15 – .95	.61	04	10.00	22	55.00	14	35.00	40
	2018	.05 – .97	.62	03	10.00	15	50.00	12	40.00	30
Management	2016	.00 – .99	.71	02	5.26	14	36.84	22	57.89	38
	2018	.10 – .97	.59	03	10.00	16	53.33	11	36.67	30

Table 5. Range, Mean, Frequency, and Percentage of CPBC falling in each category of discriminability for each subject by year

Subject	Year	Range	Mean	CPBC > .35 = Excellent		.25 ≤<= CPBC <.35 = Good		.15 ≤<= CPBC <.25 = Fair		0.00 ≤<= CPBC <.15 = Poor		CPBC < 0.00 = Flaw		Total Items f
				F	%	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%	
				Bangla	2016	-.21 – .50	.32	13	44.83	9	31.03	3	10.34	
	2018	-.10 – .30	.18	1	4.00	7	28.00	8	32.00	5	20.00	4	16.00	25
ICT	2016	.00 – .45	.21	3	8.82	10	29.41	8	23.53	12	35.29	1	2.94	34
	2018	-.02 – .38	.18	2	8.00	6	24.00	8	32.00	7	28.00	2	8.00	25
Physics	2016	.00 – .56	.37	18	56.25	5	15.63	7	21.88	1	3.13	1	3.13	32
	2018	.04 – .41	.23	3	12.00	9	36.00	6	24.00	7	28.00	0	0.00	25
Civics	2016	-.09 – .38	.25	4	10.00	23	57.50	9	22.50	2	5.00	2	5.00	40
	2018	-.12 – .43	.24	5	16.67	10	33.33	11	36.67	2	6.67	2	6.67	30
Management	2016	-.22 – .40	.23	6	15.79	12	31.58	15	39.47	2	5.26	3	7.89	38
	2018	-.30 – .37	.14	2	6.67	3	10.00	11	36.67	10	33.33	4	13.33	30

was the easiest followed by Civics, Bangla, ICT and then Physics in 2016. The picture is similar in 2018 where Civics was the easiest followed by Management, Bangla, ICT and then Physics. That is to say, science, humanities, and business are not comparable in terms of difficulty index.

The Figures 1(a) and 1(b) show that majority of the items clustered around a narrow band of

students' ability (negative1 to positive 1 ability level of examinees). Examinees on the upper left side are said to be smarter than the items on the lower right, which mean that those easier items are not difficult enough to challenge those highly proficient students. On the other hand, items on the upper right outsmart examinees on the lower left, which implies these tough items are beyond

their ability level (Yu, 2020). Visual inspection reflects that items in Figure 1(a) are better than those in Figure 1(b) in terms of matching between ability and difficulty parameters.

Figure 1(a). Person Item Map for Bangla in 2016

Figure 1(b). Person Item Map for Bangla in 2018

The Figures 2(a) and 2(b) show that majority of the items clustered around a narrow band of students' ability (negative1 to positive 1 ability level of examinees). Examinees on the upper

left side are said to be smarter or better than the items on the lower right, which mean that those easier items are not difficult enough to challenge those highly proficient students. On the other hand, items on the upper right outsmart examinees on the lower left, which implies these tough items are beyond their ability level (Yu, 2020). Visual inspection reflects that items in Figure 2(b) are better than those in Figure 2(a) in terms of matching between ability and difficulty parameters.

The Figures 3(a) show that majority of the items somewhat equal to the examinees and Figure 3(b) show that majority of the items clustered somewhat narrow band in nature of students' ability (negative1 to positive 1 ability level of examinees). Examinees on the upper left side are said to be smarter or better than the items on the lower right, which mean that those easier items are not difficult enough to challenge those highly proficient students. On the other hand, items on the upper right outsmart examinees on the lower left, which implies these tough items are beyond their ability level (Yu, 2020). Visual inspection reflects that items in Figure 3(a) are better than those in Figure 3(b) in terms of matching between ability and difficulty parameters.

Figure 2(a). Person Item Map for ICT in 2016

Figure 2(b). Person Item Map for ICT in 2018

Figure 3(a). Person Item Map for Physics in 2016

Figure 3(b). Person Item Map for Physics in 2018

Figure 4(a). Person Item Map for Civics in 2016

Figure 4(b). Person Item Map for Civics in 2018

Figure 5(b). Person Item Map for Management in 2018

Figure 5(a). Person Item Map for Management in 2016

The Figure 4(a) show that majority of the items clustered around a narrow band of students' ability (negative1 to positive 1 ability level of examinees). But the Figure 4(b) looks a bit like a histogram. Items on the upper right are not so difficult that's why a large portion of examinees have been able to respond to those items. Visual inspection reflects that items in Figure 4(b) are better than those in Figure 4(a) in terms of matching between ability and difficulty parameters.

The Figure 5(a) and 5(b) show that majority of the items are not clustered around a narrow band of students' ability (negative1 to positive 1 ability level of examinees). Examinees on the upper left side are not said to be smarter or better than the items on the lower right because those items were too much easy which is beyond their ability to response. On the other hand, items on the upper right are not so difficult that's why a large portion of examinees have been able to respond to those items. Visual inspection reflects that items in Figure 5(a) and 5(b) are not reliable in terms of ability and difficulty parameters.

Discussion

The education system of Bangladesh is massive and highly centralized. The secondary school education consists of 7 years of education including junior secondary (Grade VI-VIII), secondary (Grade IX-X), and higher secondary (Grade XI-XII). According to national statistics, over 38 million students were enrolled in formal educational institutions and among them, 3.21 million students received higher secondary (Grade XI-XII) education (BANBEIS, 2020). The higher secondary level education services is provided through three stream including general education, madrasah education, and technical vocational education. Compared to the high net enrolment (71.89%) and completion rate (62.24%) of secondary level, the net student enrolment rate (36.40%) in higher secondary level is very low (BANBEIS, 2021).

Along with the low enrolment, the high dropout rate (21.6%) indicates the poor academic performance of the higher secondary level (BANBEIS, 2021). The major factors behind these low enrolments and completion rates may include limited higher secondary education institutes, efficient teachers, lack of supportive environment, security issues (especially for girls), higher educational expense and perceived relevance (Malik, et al., 2021). However, along with these common aspect, examination system itself can be an influential factor on students' academic results. A trends analysis (Malik, et al., 2021) from 2010 to 2019 showed that student performance on the HSC national board examinations show a slightly downward trend in the pass rate, with several sharp rises and falls. In 2015, for an example, the pass rate was only 65.84 percent, the lowest rate from previous eight years due to new method of preparing and selecting question papers (BANBEIS, 2021). The examination authority explained that while earlier years, students were able to understand the question patterns consulting the previous year's question papers, however, as in 2015, each set of question papers was selected by lottery out of 28 prepared sets, students had a nonconventional question paper (Habib, 2015). In 2017, the average pass rate

of HSC examinees across the country dropped by over 5 percentage points to 66.84 due to the introduction of a "standardization of answer scripts" for examiners to follow (BANBEIS, 2021; The Daily Star, 2017). To obtain a uniform evaluation, a sample answer was provided to examiners for each subject/paper's questions by the Bangladesh Examination Development Unit (BEDU). In 2018, the pass rate dropped further to 64.55 percent after introducing a multiple sets of question papers and examinees were told only 25 minutes before the exam to prevent question leaks (BANBEIS, 2021; The Dhaka Tribune, 2018). These examples indicate that frequent changes and inadequate psychometric measures might impact on students' scores. Similarly, based upon a negative assumption and dissatisfaction about the quality of MCQ items, a decision has been taken to reduce the proportion of MCQs and increase essay types items (CQ-creative questions) HSC examinations (Chowdhury et al., 2016).

However, the findings of this study reveals that MCQ is a valid (concurrent validity measures ranged from .37 to .55 and .34 to .62 in 2016 and 2018 respectively) method to measure student performance particularly in the high-stake examination like HSC and falsify the MCQ reduction as a justified step. Another comprehensive study (Chowdhury et al., 2016) found that there is no inherent superiority of Creative Question (essay/descriptive type) over MCQ or vice versa and each of them caters different need of test objectives. Chowdhury et al., (2016) further suggested that both Creative and MCQ should be given equal weight in the public examination.

MCQ carries higher reliability in marking and covers a wide range of content (Kamal & Mullick, 2020). In the present study, the reliability analysis of MCQ part of the HSC examination showed that the reliability coefficient of 2016 (.69 to .81) was higher than the coefficient (.52 to .74) of 2018. It can be noted that the reliability and validity of MCQ was comparatively higher than 2018. Similar earlier studies (Kamal & Mullick, 2020; Chowdhury et al., 2016) support this findings and suggested MCQ to remain

as an important component for objective measurement.

Further Kamal and Mullick (2020) argued that existing teachers could construct quality MCQ questions for students' assessment. The present study found that the items of 2016 was better distributed in terms of difficulty index, discrimination index and item-person map than those of 2018. It seems that the reduction of MCQ items (reduced by 10%) from 2016 to 2018 may have caused the discrepancies in MCQ test formation across the years. When a test has limited number of items, it often fails to spread the items over difficulty index, discrimination index and item-person map in appropriate proportion. Which may identify only a narrow band of student ability. In addition, the notion that reliability of a test also increases with number of items of the test (Abdelmoula, Chakroun, & Akrouf, 2015, Cronbach, 1951) also supports the findings of the present study.

Despite teachers are experienced and good at developing test item, there is no alternative but to put greater importance on imparting rigorous training on educational measurement and psychometrics. It is not doubt that developing test items (both CQ and MCQ) for large scale public examination is a highly technical and need necessary capacity to build joint effort and large repository of MCQ and CQ questions. Test developed may need to go through training on regular item analysis to develop and improve quality items, validity and reliability of questions.

The study further reveals that a test with appropriate psychometric property can assess best student Chowdhury et al., 2016ents low to higher order cognitive skills. This discussion opens new avenue for the testing approach in Bangladesh particularly when the public examinations are at high stake due to widespread pandemic. The general paper-pen tests/ examinations are now slowly being replaced by the online internet based testing system sometimes referred as e-examination system or Computer Based Testing (CBT) employing MCQ items (Khan, 2017; Ranganth et al., 2017). The study described how an Online MCQ Test

System could be conducted through the internet for remote students. Study (Ranganth et al., 2017) shows that test taker perceived MCQs as sufficient to test knowledge during their course. However, moving assessment to online simply not putting the "existing examination items in an online format without consideration for other critical aspects of the testing process (Diego et al., 2020). The study suggests that along with the changes in the existing paper based examination delivery format, items of the high-stake examination need to be "piloted, evaluated, and adjusted accordingly to meet the content and psychometric standards". Thus, Multiple Choice Question (MCQ) developed carefully through all psychometric properties could have all potential to assess all level of cognitive aspects proving.

The HSC examination is not only the output record of the last school examination, but also carries high value to enter the higher education. One must pass HSC examination and obtain a fixed score to sit for the university entrance examination in Bangladesh (Rahman, 2020). A number of pressing issues impede the growth of in higher secondary education subsector particularly efficient assessment of learning due to lack of expertise and multiple authorities. The higher secondary education sub-sector spreads over school to post graduate colleges in terms of academic attachment. The curriculum is provided by the central National Curriculum and Textbook Board (NCTB), academic supervision, approval and affiliation are administrated by the Boards of Intermediate and Secondary Education and administration is run either local governing bodies or Directorate of Secondary and Higher Education (DSHE). These multi-stakeholder governance often negatively contribute to the purpose, curriculum implementation, teaching-learning, assessment and outcomes (Malik et al., 2021). Thus strong alignment between curriculum and assessment is need to be ensured so that high-stake public examination can measure what students learn. Developing test items should consider coverage the content and measure understanding, application, analyse knowledge and facts as

well. Test questions must have the ability to test a range of skills at increasing levels of difficulty.

Conclusion

High-stakes examinations is prevalent across different level of education throughout Asia including Bangladesh. While examinations are designed to measure learners' knowledge and skills, yet high stakes examination in this regions sometimes had overwhelming power to influences attitudes towards teaching-learning and social expectations and pressure (Al-amin & Janinka, 2018). In addition, higher secondary education (Grades XI and XII) plays a bridging role between secondary and tertiary education in Bangladesh. The public examination (HSC) completion upon this two-year education level directs graduates' stream of higher education and future career path. The present study reveals that frequent changes and contextualization of any assessment procedure might impact on students testing scores. Further, being sandwiched in between school and higher education, the higher secondary subsector is often remained under researched particularly how the hugely loaded academic year and activities are being assessed. A knowledge and evidence based assessment approach may enhance the functionality of this high stake assessment. A set of efficient Multiple Choice Questions (MCQ) can tap the students' knowledge, skills and higher order cognitive functioning. Findings indicate that an extended need of research may help the revision of existing Higher Secondary Education assessment procedure. This may further address to explore alternative access to blended and online assessment to ensure continuation of studies in crisis situations such as the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and beyond.

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